

“FUNDING OF CENTRAL UNIVERSITIES AND HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEMS IN INDIA”

GUIDANCE

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ABSTRACT: *Education is one of the significant factors instrumental in the development of a country. And Education is the backbone of every country. A country will not be able to survive in the competitive world if its education system is not capable of contributing to its development. To develop India as an education hub or to become a prosperous partner within the world economy, India must qualitatively strengthen education normally and better education with research and development in particular. This paper aims to identify budget, funding and emerging issues challenges and suggestions in the field of Higher Education in India. The study uses secondary data from available sources.*

KEYWORDS: *Higher Education, Budget, Funding, Issues, Challenges, and Suggestions;*

01. INTRODUCTION

In the effective functioning of any system, the constituents of the system play an important role. Indeed the efficiency of the system largely depends on the efficient working of these constituents. India has a multi-level system of educational planning and management. At present, there are three levels of control in the area of education: (I) Central Government level, (II) State Government level, (III) District level. Elementary education (Classes I-VIII) come under the direct administrative responsibility of districts, the state government accepts the whole school education and shares the responsibilities with universities, the University Grant Commission (UGC) and the Union Government in the field of higher education. The central Government, according to the constitution, is directly responsible for the planning and management of central universities, research and the scientific and technical institution of national importance, and maintenance of the quality and standards in higher education. Both central and state Government have also established autonomous intuitions (which are funded from the public exchequer), which have own administration and control, and in case of the educational system particularly higher educational system, teacher, teaching materials, modern educational infrastructure, their recruitment, and management are extremely important to the efficient and effective functioning of the system. For this purpose, a huge amount of funds are required. Therefore the nature and extent of availability of funds and their management become the key factor in the efficient working of the higher educational institutions. There are multiple sources of finances for education in India. These sources will be broadly speaking classified into external and internal or domestic sources of finance. External sources don't a kind major part of academic finances in the Republic of India. The domestic sources of funding are broadly speaking divided into public and personal sources. The public sources include contributions created by central, state and native governments. The private or non-governmental sources include fees and other household expenditures incurred by the direct beneficiaries (students/parents) of education and endowments and donations made by individuals, trusts, etc. Among the private sources, fees are compulsory payments whereas others are voluntary contributions. However, the basic question arising in this context is whether the universities have a system of financing? If so, how efficient is it? Who all are the players in this system of management? Who is going to take responsibility if the question of success or failure in the financial management of the university?

Here, it may be pertinent to describe some of the aspects of financing universities. Accordingly, there are three major sources for financing universities in India. They are:

1. Government (by the way of grants),
2. Students (by the way of fees),
3. Private donors (by the way of endowments).

02. HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

Higher education is of significant importance for the country because it could be a powerful tool to create the knowledge-based society of the 21st Century. India's higher education system is under pressure from the State and an increasingly educated youth population to achieve multiple objectives, such as growth, quality, and equitable access. To reach these political targets, national and provincial policymakers take an activist approach, such as providing adequate resources, enabling the private provision of higher education, and so forth. With the growing size and variety of the upper education sector significantly in terms of courses, management, and geographical coverage, it has become necessary to have governance in higher The education Government has set a target of increasing the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) from the present level of about 12% to 15% by the end of the XI Five yrs Plan and to 30% by the year 2020. Various new initiatives are being taken by the govt to extend the GER. To manage the efforts taken by the government, it requires complete governance of higher education.

Higher education institutions in India are of varied growth levels and also have varying funding mechanisms. We have higher education institutions under the category of Institutes of national importance like IITs, IIMs, AIIMS and the Central universities, all funded 100% by the Central Government. State Universities are funded mainly by the State Government, however,

some marginal financial supports are provided by the Central Government as plan grants through various schemes of the UGC. The number of universities up to the year 2019 has been reported to be 907 by the UGC.

Table-I reveals that there has been appreciable growth of Higher Education since 1951. The number of university-level institutions and colleges has grown up from 28 to 907 and 578 to +44000 (Approx) respectively from 1951 to 2019. As a result, the no. of teachers, as well as students, has also increased significantly. The increase's students" enrollment is over the expansion of the no. of lecturers over the period of time, may be due to the massive investment by Govt. at school level in style of primary furthermore as pedagogy. Rise in enrolments and institutions at the school level, there is mushrooming growth in higher education institutions at the end of 2019 there were 907 Universities and +44000 colleges in India. But still, we need more than 1200 universities to cater to the demand. The table 1 shows that our education system is improving not only in the number of colleges and universities but also in enrolment. Most of these universities have affiliated colleges where undergraduate courses are approved and taught. But still, if we compare this improving stat with an increasing population, then we have to rethink, is it still improving.

TABLE-I
Growth of Higher Education Institutions and Their Intake Capacity in India:

YEAR—► Institutions & Enrolment	1951	1961	1971	1981	1991	2001	2011	2019
No. of University	28	45	93	123	177	266	659	907
No. of Colleges	578	1816	3227	4738	7347	11145	33023	44000+
No. of Teachers (in 000")	24	62	190	244	272	395	575	---
No. of Students Enroll (in 000")	174	557	1956	2752	4925	8399	22373	54000+

TABLE-II
UNIVERSITY-LEVEL INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA:

Universities	Total No.
State Universities	399
Deemed to be Universities	125
Central Universities	49
Private Universities	334
Total	907

03. BUDGET OF UNIVERSITIES IN INDIA

With this basic background, now an analysis of the budgetary system adopted by Central Universities in general particular is made, indicating the need for budgetary reforms. As already discussed there are four parts of accounts as suggested by the UGC in its model budget;

Part I Maintenance Grant account; for established Universities which have passed one stage of the plan period, it will be non-plan account,

Part II Plan Account (General and Specific Schemes),

Part III Earmarked' Special Funds (ESP) (mainly, fellowship, seminar, and projects accounts),

Part IV Debt, Deposit, and Advances (DDA) account.

It would be relevant here to point out that **Part I to Part III** accounts may also have two sections Revenue and Capital accounts. The revenue part of the accounts is shown under Income and Expenditure Account and the capital investments are taken to the Balance Sheet.

Part IV, Debt, Deposits and Advances account is prepared by the finance section.

The major operational part of the budget is planned under Part-I maintenance account and the expenditure relating to academic departments is prepared by the Heads of the Departments/Deans and submitted to the Finance Department, where it is centrally collected and vetted to suit the level of funds expected or available.

04. FUNDING OF CENTRAL UNIVERSITIES IN INDIA

Kind of Grants Available:

There are two kinds of grants for universities, institutions deemed to be universities and colleges, they are:

- Development (Plan) Grants
- Maintenance (Non-Plan) Grants

Central universities and faculties related to them and institutions deemed to be universities receive each the setup and non-plan grants. However, the state universities and their attached colleges receive only set up grants. The objective of providing set up help isn't only to boost the infrastructure and basic facilities within the universities therefore on succeed a minimum of the brink level however also to develop excellence in those that are already ahead. These are not intended to supplement the requirements under the maintenance grants.

The UGC provides Non-Plan assistance to universities to meet the recurring expenditure on salaries of non-teaching and teaching staff and for maintenance of laboratories, libraries, buildings, as also for obligatory payments such as taxes, telephone bills, electricity, and other purposes. Development assistance is utilized for the consolidation of existing infrastructure and for modernizing teaching, research, and administration and to meet the changing demands of the society.

A. Funding for Universities:

There is a difference in the funding pattern of central universities, institutions deemed to be universities and colleges of state universities. We can look at the pattern of them separately. All funding is divided into two heads, i.e., Maintenance and Development Grants.

I. Maintenance Grant:

The exact quantity of maintenance grant collectible to central universities and institutions deemed to be universities is determined on the "covering of deficit" basis, i.e., the internal receipt is deducted out of the actual expenditure incurred in any year. No institution will build up any reserve out of the maintenance grant paid to that. This grant will increase incrementally for each institution once a year, with the size of increment varying from institution to institution.

Policy: Each central university and institution deemed to be university has a Finance Committee comprising representatives of the university, local educationists and a nominee each from UGC and the Ministry of Human Resources Development (HRD) (usually the Financial Advisor). In the case of a central university, it is headed by Vice Chancellor. It is responsible for the preparation of maintenance and development budgets. The prevailing practice is that each one item of recurring expenditure in a current set up period and sanctioned by UGC on the basis of approved norms are enclosed at the end of the plan period in the nonplan sector under the same norms and patterns.

Practice: For maintenance grants, the university prepares the budget and revised budget in September-October and get them duly approved by the Finance Committee and Executive Council. The representative of UGC and also the financial consultant make sure that the proposals enclosed in a budget are in accordance with the rules on the topic. The maintenance grants are subject to negotiations between the UGC, the HRD Ministry, and the planning Department.

II. Development Grants:

These are sanctioned to universities for their expansion activities and for developing new programs. As the universities develop their maintenance grants but the size of development grants does not increase proportionately.

Procedure: In the case of development grants, UGC analyses the past performance of central universities, their lines of development and needs. UGC also estimates the availability of resources based on allocation made in the past. Then UGC formulates its proposals for the plan period, which includes plan programs of universities and presents them to government. These proposals are then finalized after detailed discussions between UGC and the government. Then they are going before the Planning Commission for final allocation. After indicating the provisional allocation of funds of each of the central universities, UGC calls for detailed proposals. The plans are scrutinized by expert committees at the headquarters after holding discussions with universities.

B. Funding for Institutions Deemed to be Universities:

Section 3 of the UGC Act provides that the Central Government may on the advice of the Commission, by notification in the official Gazette, declare any institution for higher education other than a university that is doing very higher standards in a very specific, as an institution Deemed to be University. Such a declaration entitles the institution of all support as provided for within the UGC Act. The institution also has the power to confer degrees and develop and innovate academic programs on its own. Such institutions enjoy the academic status and privileges of a university and are able to strengthen their activities in the field of their specialization,

rather than becoming a multi-faculty university of a general type. These institutions aren't figured on the standard university system; in spite, they achieve recognition through excellence in their academic pursuits and innovative practices. These institutions need a large measure of academic autonomy and functional freedom.

C. Funding for State Universities:

According to Section 12 (B) of the UGC Act, new State Universities established when 17th June 1972, shall not be eligible to receive any grant from the Central Government, UGC, or any other organization receiving funds from the State Government, unless the Commission satisfies itself as per the prescribed norms and procedures, that such a university is fit to receive grants. As on 31 March 2002, there were 178 universities, recognized by the UGC.

Funding for Colleges: Development of colleges are an important area from the point of view of maintenance of standards and equalization of educational opportunities for the disadvantaged and differently abled section of society because colleges are responsible in a major way for undergraduate education and to a great extent account for post-graduate education. With a view to removing disparities and regional imbalances, special grants are also being provided to the colleges catering to the needs of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, women students and for intensive development of colleges located in backward/rural/border areas.

UGC gives plan and non-plan grants to central universities and plans grants to state universities but these grants do not go to affiliated colleges of the universities, in spite, they go for university campus only. For affiliated colleges, UGC gives a separate grant. Therefore, for the attached colleges to state universities, UGC provides maintenance grants.

The UGC has decentralised its functioning by opening seven regional offices inside the country since 1994 for easy access and speedy release of grants below varied schemes/programs regarding the college sector. Grants to all the eligible colleges all over the country are being disbursed by these UGC regional offices under the following schemes/programs being dealt with:

- ❖ College development programs (UG/PG);
- ❖ Faculty development program (Teacher Fellowships);
- ❖ Construction of hostels for women (Special Scheme);
- ❖ Minor research projects (for college teachers);
- ❖ Conferences, seminars and symposia;
- ❖ Autonomous colleges (release of grants only);
- ❖ The revival of old reputed colleges (on time special grant);
- ❖ Facilities for disadvantaged groups (visually handicapped teachers);
- ❖ College science improvement program (COSIP);
- ❖ College humanities and social science improvement program (COHSSIP);

Autonomous Colleges: The scheme of autonomous colleges was formulated by the UGC in the fourth five year plan (1969-73). These colleges themselves prescribe their curriculum and conduct the evaluation of their students through a system of continuous evaluation. An autonomous college has freedom to:

- Determine and prescribe its own course;
- Prescribe rules for admission in consonance with the reservation policy of the State Government;
- Evolve methods of assessment of student work, the conduct of examination, and notification of results;
- Use of modern tools of education technology to achieve higher standard and greater creativity.

05. ISSUE AND CHALLENGES: AN ANALYSIS

India has been a multi-cultural, multi-religious, and multi-linguistic society. Every State has a different and distinct identity. Dealing with various aspirations of such people in a democratic country is indeed a challenge to the Government of India. The various issues are outlined here:

❖ Lack of Quality Education:

In the top 100 universities list by 'Times Higher Education World Reputation Rankings', none of the Indian universities could be found in the list. In the 2017 rankings by the HRD ministry, only 2,995 institutions (6%) participated from around 51,000-strong higher educational institutions in India. There is severe regional imbalance too. In the overall rankings, of the 100 best institutions, 67 are from just 8th states. Among the best 100 universities, 40 are in three states. Among the best 100 colleges, 77 are from just five states (Nanda, Prashant K. 2017).

❖ Corruption in Education:

Corruption in the Indian education system has been eroding the quality of education. It is one of the major contributors to domestic black money. Payment to Management at dark rooms and seeking admissions is increasing. 'Get full salary in the account, pay back part to Management by blank signed cheque is also a practice in some private schools.

❖ No Proper Value Education:

Value education is not offered in schools and colleges.

If offered, religion and emotion are spread within the name important education.

Many of the doctors, lawyers, CA, politicians and Government servants who are supposed to be the saviors of the society, suffer from serious charges of corruption. Old-age homes are increasing. Suicides are increasing. The meaning of love is eventually changing. The education-led technology, inventions, and innovations are being misused.

❖ Public School Workforce Absenteeism:

Teacher absenteeism in India is exorbitant. World Bank estimates show the cost of salaries paid to absent teachers is the US \$2 billion every year.

In a study by Kremer, etc, they found 24% of private sector teachers and 41% of public sector medical workers were absent during the survey. Absence rates among them ranged from 14.6% in Maharashtra to 41.9% in Jharkhand. Overemphasis on academic qualifications by the University Grants Commission (UGC) has resulted in a number of university teachers registering for Ph.D. programs. It is not a passion for research but the passion for climbing up the career ladder in the form of promotion that motivates teachers to register for a Ph.D. As a result, the quality of most Ph.D. research is sub-standard and our Indian universities have highly qualified but highly unproductive academics. India cannot build internationally recognized research-oriented universities night long, however, the country has the key components in place to start and sustain the method. India can get to create a dozen or more universities that may compete internationally to completely participate in the new world economy. Without these universities, India is destined to stay a scientific backwater.

06. SUGGESTIONS:

The following suggestions are put for the improvement of the quality of higher education in the country:

- I.** Need-based job-oriented courses should be provided in colleges and universities that would fulfill the skill-based educational needs of the society.
- II.** Special grants to universities and colleges in backward areas should be provided to improve their infrastructure and facilitate innovations and thereby become internationally respected.
- III.** Students from economically backward families must essentially be given a fully subsidized education.
- IV.** Liberal funding of higher education and the creation of funds through donations, an upward revision of fee structure, raising funds from corporate sources should be considered by the governments in the Centre and States.

CONCLUSION

India's higher education system is under pressure from the State and an increasingly educated youth population to achieve multiple objectives, such as growth, quality, and equitable access. To reach these political targets, national and provincial policymakers take an activist approach, such as providing adequate resources, enabling the private provision of higher education, and so forth. Issues concerning the interaction with the Governments, statutory bodies, etc. are issues of external governance of higher education systems/institutions. Likewise, the problems of academic and administrative matters of the institution; and matters of its own vision and mission are thought of as problems with internal governance within. The focus of governance was on regulating quality standards. The constituent colleges were largely privately owned and lightly regulated regarding costs, access, and equity. Since colonial government jobs—the ambition of most graduates—have a relatively tiny group of college-educated Indians high status and relatively high income, they were willing to pay for it. The report recommended decentralization within the university hierarchy, including empowering university deans, shifting responsibility for course regulation, examinations and degree awards to affiliated colleges, and recommending that universities concentrate on —postgraduate education and research programs. The report also recommended that UGC's activities be shared with State Councils for Higher Education.

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